

Recommended citation: Cooke, N. J., Theofanous, M., Saadat, M., & Hawwash, K. I. M. (2018). Embedding the SDGs into Interdisciplinary Engineering PBL: A Case Study: Structural Mechatronics Integrated Design Project. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 699-706). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672669.

Embedding the SDGs into Interdisciplinary Engineering PBL:

A Case Study: Structural Mechatronics Integrated Design Project

NJ Cooke¹ ; M Theofanous; M Saadat; KIM Hawwash

School of Engineering
University of Birmingham
Birmingham, United Kingdom
E-mail: n.j.cooke@bham.ac.uk

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development, Sustainable Development Goals in Engineering Education

Keywords: SDG, Sustainability, Sulitest, Interdisciplinary, PBL

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability is an increasingly important part of an engineers' practice, requiring active participation to counter the global threats to humanity. Sustainability Engineering Education chiefly focusses on design considerations for emissions, energy and materials e.g. reducing pollution, renewable technologies and whole lifecycle analyses. Cultivating a broader working knowledge of sustainability in Engineering Education beyond the technological aspects risks being perceived as non-essential. We focus on the introduction of the United Nations 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the curriculum and their potential role to encourage sustainability learning. We present a case study of how SDG knowledge is embedded into a multidisciplinary PBL experience – the Integrated Design Project (IDP), which involves designing real-world structural mechatronics applications for mechanical, electrical, civil, and materials disciplines. We use this case study to address 3 research questions in embedding SDGs into Education, which are derived from the broader set proposed in a recent review of this literature by Thürer et al [1] :

¹ Corresponding Author
NJ, Cooke
n.j.cooke@bham.ac.uk

- 1) Implemented practice: Which approach is best suited to expose students to SDGs and what tools should be used?
- 2) Student's values versus knowledge: What is the relationship between student's SDG knowledge and their values?
- 3) Outcomes: How does the student adoption of SDGs outcomes evolve over time?

This paper proceeds as follows: Section 1 provides some background including a brief outline of SDGs and the Sulitest. Sections 2, 3 and 4 address the research questions using case study evidence. Section 5 concludes with a discussion of the key findings, impact, limitations and future work.

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 The SDGs and their Means of Implementations

The UN General Assembly adopted 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) [2] in September 2015 as part of the "Transforming our World: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development 2030 Development Agenda". The SDGs are underpinned by 169 targets with 231 progress indicators, and 7 "Means of Implementation" (MOI). The SDG titles are stated in *Fig.1* and *Fig.2*. The SDGs manifest through three perspectives: the environment, society and the economy. They are not legally binding, but public interest is rising; e.g. google trends data for global web searching of SDGs from January 2016 to January 2018 indicates a doubling of searches.

The SDG Agenda outlines several MOI categories: Trade; Finance; Technology; Capacity Building; Policy and Institutional Coherence; Multi-stakeholder Partnerships; Data monitoring and Accountability [3]. MOI categories can be grouped across three domains: Financial, Institutional and Technological. For Engineers, the Technological domain MOIs are most relevant, and are defined as i) general research and development of technologies, and ii) technology sharing with developing economies. All MOIs are interdependent e.g., the MOI Climate financing and Environmental Impact Assessments, would support the MOI Biodiversity technology developments and their transfer to developing countries [4]. Interdependencies are considered essential to realising any SDG, and consequently SDG017: Partnerships for Goals, is dedicated exclusively to identifying and cultivating them.

1.2 Sustainability knowledge and literacy

To successfully embed SDGs in Engineering Education, students must understand them. A tool to assist this is the Sustainability Literacy Test (Sulitest) [5], an online test comprising of 30 "core" Multiple-Choice Questions (MCQ) which address global sustainability issues, with an option for 20 further questions specific to locality or discipline. Responses provide an indication of knowledge against global and national benchmarks for individual SDGs, and, more reliably, four broader knowledge categories which are listed in *Table 1*. Sulitest questions are wide and varied e.g. scientific knowledge "Which one of the following is NOT a greenhouse gas?"; social

sciences “*In 2012, how many people around the world have been victims of forced labour?*”, and more broader systems thinking related to Engineering “*A complex system ... can operate important changes when acting on sensitive points called “leverage points”... which is the least effective for achieving systemic changes?*”. Experiences in using the Sulitest at Nordic Engineering faculties acknowledge its value as a teaching tool despite variability in question type and quality, such as the varied use of statistics in MCQ answers [6].

1.3 Embedding sustainability into interdisciplinary PBL

Four approaches were evaluated for embedding general sustainability into curricula from several thousand module descriptions in [7]. These were i) exposure to environmental issues in existing modules, ii) specific sustainability modules, iii) as distinct programme-level specialisation and iv) intertwined as a concept into modules. The latter was found to be most effective. Likewise, in this work, we embed the SDGs into an Interdisciplinary PBL module – the IDP. This approach is discussed and endorsed by [8] with caveats: the need to consider underdeveloped group work skills and student difficulties in relating to other disciplines. Once taught the SDG framework, and taking the Sulitest, students can express how their work can progress each goal. E.g. Designing a large moving structure in a city such as an Observation Wheel, could address SDG08 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) via the target 8.9 (policies to promote sustainable tourism) which is measured by indicator (8.9.2 Number of jobs).

2 IMPLEMENTED PRACTICE

Which approach is best suited to expose students to SDGs and what tools should be used? To answer this, we present an outline of how the SDGs are embedded in the IDP and evaluate student performance.

2.1 The Integrated Design Project (IDP)

The Integrated Design Project (IDP) is a 200-hour 2nd year Interdisciplinary PBL module with the theme “Kinetic Architecture through Structural Mechatronics”. Students collaborate in interdisciplinary teams to produce reference designs for large moving structures located across the world e.g. bridges, stadium roofs and observation wheels. The project specifications and assessments are developed with a leading global engineering consultancy (Arup) to ensure authenticity. The Learning Outcomes (LO) are designed to foster interdisciplinarity [9]. They are 1) Demonstrate skills in multidisciplinary team-based sustainable engineering design and 2) Develop an individual disciplinary identity and competence. Students undertake “Design Impact Sessions” in Project management; Sustainability; Health and Safety; Enterprise; Design process methods; Emerging technology research; Model-based Simulation and Design. The IDP is modelled on best-practice interdisciplinary PBL modules from other institutions e.g. [10].

2.2 IDP Sustainability Learning Outcomes

Sustainability is embedded into IDP via 3 LOs of which the first 2 relate to SDGs. These are: 1) Develop a broad understanding of sustainability via SDGs which achieved through background reading of materials and taking the Sulitest; 2) Develop an understanding of the SDGs and how the project could progress them which is achieved through group discussions about the value of SDGs to their project. For completeness, the additional LO is 3) Identify the main sources of embodied and operational carbon and energy and the end-of-life scenario for your project. Sustainability LO are assessed at the end module through answering the question *“What is your project’s impact on the wider world?”* with evidence to meet the following assessment criteria: *“The impact of the solution on the wider world is clear from how you propose to progress the SDGs. The conceptual and discipline-specific design summaries give clear evidence of full quantitative and qualitative consideration of open (energy) and closed (materials) ecosystems, and how your structure will help answer local people’s needs e.g. land use, gender equality, education, culture, production and consumption, life cycles, value chains, water, energy and food”.*

2.3 Sulitest Results

IDP Students (n=335) complete the Sulitest mid-way through learning i.e. after 100 study hours. Results from the 2017 cohort (*Table 1*) report their core knowledge is 56% correct answers, which is comparable to the national and worldwide average, and previously published results for Nordic Engineering students (53%, n=700) [6]. Scores for the four broader knowledge categories shows greatest positive difference in personal responsibility and the individual role to play. The weaker scores come from knowledge of the transitioning towards sustainability, which suggests to us that MOIs should be a focus of SDG learning.

Table 1. Students Sulitest performance (n=355) against benchmarks

Knowledge Category	% correct		
	Students	National	Worldwide
Sustainable humanity and ecosystems	63	64	59
Global and local human-constructed systems	56	58	54
Transition towards sustainability	49	51	51
Role to play, individual & systemic change	53	50	50
All Questions:	56	57	54

Sulitest performance against each SDG (Figure 2) indicates a cohort’s relative knowledge level with respect to an SDG, however it could also simply indicate relative question difficulty.

Fig. 1. Sulitest results measuring relative knowledge of 2nd year Engineering cohort (n=335)

3 STUDENT'S VALUES VERSUS KNOWLEDGE

3.1 SDGs valued by student groups as applicable to practice

What is the relationship between student's SDG knowledge and their values? Project groups (n=46) comprising 5-8 students are asked to select 3 SDGs they deem most valuable. There are 3 clear SDGs (Fig. 2) selected by over half of the groups: SDG08, SDG09 and SDG10. These popular SDGs are candidates for greater focus when teaching SDGs. Comparing knowledge against values (Fig. 1 vs Fig. 2) reveals some similar rankings e.g. SDG13 and SDG08, however, in general, similarities are weak.

Fig. 2. SDGs valued by project groups (n=46)

Further insight comes from looking at the set of SDGs valued by each group. A Pearson correlation coefficient is calculated on the SDGs selected together. Focussing on the top 5 SDGs selected by groups students to improve reliability, the correlation matrix is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Pearson correlation of valued SDGs by project groups (n=46)

SDG	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
8	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.1	1.0	0.1	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1
9	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2
10	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.0	1.0	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
12	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	1.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
13	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	1.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1

Overall there are more negative correlations than positive correlations between the most popular SDG choices e.g. Decent work and Economic Growth (SDG08) has a strong negative correlation (-0.27) with Reduced Inequality (SDG10). Reasons for negative correlations could be the omission of goals that are perceived to have similar meanings to those already selected. Conversely, Responsible consumption and production (SDG12) and Climate Action (SDG13) are positively correlated. Reasons for positive correlations could be the selection of complementary SDGs which have casual effects on each other. These observations highlight the need to relate SDGs to each other, ensure less technological SDGs are valued, and potential groupings.

3.2 Progression of valued SDGs by Means of Implementation (MOIs)

Groups are asked to describe how their projects would advance their valued SDGs to develop their MOI understanding. Their MOI responses are coded into logical sets and summarised in *Table 3*.

Table 3. Project group (n=46) identified MOIs and their SDGs

Group identified MOIs (coded)	Group Valued SDGs	Official MOI type(s)
Education/employment/Trade opportunities	1,2,3,4,7,8,9,11,	Capacity Building
Healthy lifestyle choices	3,11,	Policy and Institutional Coherence.
Profit reinvestment in public services	4,7,	Finance, Policy and Institutional Coherence.
Sustainable/green energies	7,12	Technology
Civic pride: provide inspiration	7,8,9,11	Multi-stakeholder partnerships
sustainable material sourcing and recycling technologies.	3,9,11,12,13,15	Technology
Environment protection: natural habitats and water conservation	1,3,6,14	Policy and Institutional Coherence.

Comparing groups identification of MOIs to official categories demonstrates that the students can intuitively identify MOIs from most categories. There are two MOIs that appear for several SDGs: Education/Employment and Trade Opportunities, and Sustainable Materials and Recycling Technologies. Interestingly, SDGs relating to Inequality (SDG05 and SDG10) are valued by groups but did not have identified MOIs; there is an ongoing challenge to relate non-technological SDGs to Engineers.

4 OUTCOMES

How does student adoption of SDGs outcomes evolve over time? We examine sample assessed output (Figure 3) from a high-achieving group at the end of their 200 hours IDP learning and compare it to a similar report they submitted midway through learning. The chief difference is the inclusion of SDG10 (Reduce inequality) with suitable MOIs, and SDG12 referring to specific design information. This demonstrates a successful integration of the SDGs into sustainability learning.

Fig. 3. Example of assessed Sustainability Learning Outcomes

5 DISCUSSION

Embedding SDGs into Engineering Education could fundamentally change Engineers thoughts and action for the benefit of the planet. A case study embedding SDGs in Interdisciplinary PBL addressed three research questions: “Which approach is best suited to expose students to SDGs and what tools should be used”, “What is the relationship between student’s SDG knowledge and their values?” and “How does the student adoption of SDGs outcomes evolve over time?”. Post-instruction Sulitest results measured SDG knowledge and compare it to national and international historical baselines to provide measures of student progression. Cultivating student engagement by relating valued SDGs to projects via implementation provides insights into how students relate them. SDG-oriented learning outcomes and assessment, logical groupings, and prioritisation are useful mechanisms and guidelines for engineering educators wishing to embed SDGs into their curriculum via interdisciplinary PBL.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Matthias Thürer, I. Tomašević, M. Stevenson, T. Qu and D. Huisingsh, "A systematic review of the literature on integrating sustainability into engineering curricula," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, pp. 608-617, 2018.
- [2] D. Griggs, M. Stafford-Smith, O. Gaffney, J. Rockström, M. C. Öhman, P. Shyamsundar, W. Steffen, G. Glaser, N. Kanie and I. Noble, "Policy: Sustainable development goals for people and planet," *Nature*, vol. 495, no. 7441, p. 305, 2013.
- [3] M. Stafford-Smith, D. Griggs, O. Gaffney and e. al., "Integration: the key to implementing the Sustainable Development Goals," *Sustainability Science*, vol. 12, p. 911, 2017.
- [4] S. H. Olsen, E. Zusman, I. Miyazawa, T. Cadman, T. Yoshida and M. Bengtsson, "Implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): An Assessment of the Means of Implementation(MOI)," in *ISAP*, 2014.
- [5] A. Décamps, G. Barbat, J. C. Carteron, V. Hands and C. Parkes, "Sulitest: A collaborative initiative to support and assess sustainability literacy in higher education.," *The International Journal of Management Education*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 138-152, 2017.
- [6] M. Karvinen, T. Grindsted, A. Keranen, J. Hermansen, L. Selbekk and S. Sohlo, "Sustainability literacy and engineering: Experiences from a literacy test as a teaching and assessment tool in Nordic universities," in *SEFI 2017*, 2017.
- [7] R. Lozano, "Diffusion of sustainable development in universities' curricula: an empirical example from Cardiff University," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 18, no. 7, pp. 637-644, 2010.
- [8] B. Sharma, B. Steward, S. Ong and F. Miguez, "Evaluation of teaching approach and student learning in a multidisciplinary sustainable engineering course," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 142, no. 4, pp. 4032-4040, 2017.
- [9] E. J. Spelt, H. J. Biemans, H. Tobi, P. A. Luning and M. Mulder, "Teaching and learning in interdisciplinary higher education: A systematic review," *Educational Psychology Review*, vol. 21, no. 4, p. 365, 2009.
- [10] S. Bains, J. E. Mitchell, A. Nyamapfene and E. Tilley, "Work in progress: Multi-disciplinary curriculum review of engineering education. UCL's integrated engineering programme," in *Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)*, 2015.